

TENSILE AND COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR OF ARALL AND GLARE

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ABSTRACT

Material characterisation tests were conducted on ARALL3 and GLARE3 which consist of thin sheets of aluminium alloy bonded together with aramid and glass fiber reinforced preregs respectively. The tension test results are found to agree well with predictions based on the rule of mixtures, especially when the residual stresses introduced by post-stretching of the laminates are taken into account. The compressive strengths are found to be limited by plastic buckling of the aluminium layers. In the case of the unsymmetrically laminated GLARE3-2/1, they are further diminished by coupling between bending and extensional behaviour.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid developments in the aerospace field have given rise to a number of innovative alternatives to the traditional materials used for airframe construction. The dominance of aluminium alloys in the field has been challenged in the last few decades by fibre reinforced polymer composites which offer higher specific strengths and longer fatigue lives. The shift towards composites, however, has been restrained because of their low impact resistance, high costs and poor machinability. The last decade has seen the emergence of a new class of hybrid materials called fibre metal laminates which strike a middle ground combining desirable characteristics of both composites and metals [1-3]. They consist of thin sheets of aluminium alloy bonded together with fibre reinforced adhesive prepreg. The outer aluminium layers provide impact resistance, damage inspectability and machinability, while the inner composite layers provide damage tolerance, superior fatigue life and high specific strength and stiffness.

ARALL-3 and GLARE-3 are two specific forms of fibre metal laminates currently available in the market. The former has aramid fibre reinforced prepreg sandwiched between sheets of alloy 7475-T76, while the latter employs R-glass fibre reinforcement and alloy 2024-T3. Material characterisation tests were performed at the Institute for Aerospace Research of the National Research Council of Canada on specific configurations of the two products, as part of a preliminary assessment for research investigation into their shear buckling characteristics. The tests served to bring out response characteristics specific to fiber metal laminates which are reported in this work. The results are in good agreement with previously published data and predictions using rule of mixtures. The theory was modified to take into account the effects of residual stresses introduced by the curing process and post-stretching of the laminates.

TEST SET UP AND SPECIFICATIONS

TEST MATERIAL

The test material was procured commercially from the Structural Laminates Company of Pennsylvania. ARALL3 was obtained in the 3/2 configuration, while GLARE3 was in the 2/1 configuration. Both materials were supplied in large sheet sizes (1200 mm x 2400 mm) from which coupons were cut as required for the tests.

ARALL3-3/2 consists of three layers of aluminium alloy 7475-T761 alternating with two unidirectional plies of aramid fibre reinforced prepreg (AFRP). The direction of fibre reinforcement is aligned with the rolling direction of the aluminium. The nominal aluminium sheet thickness was 0.305 mm while the AFRP layers had a thickness of about 0.216 mm, providing a total nominal thickness of 1.35 mm for the laminate.

GLARE3-2/1 consists of two layers of aluminium alloy 2024-T3, each 0.203 mm thick, bonded together with R-glass fibre reinforced epoxy prepreg (GFRP). The GFRP is actually a cross-ply arrangement consisting of two individual layers, a zero and a ninety degree ply, each with a thickness of about 0.127 mm. The nominal thickness of the GLARE3-2/1 laminate was therefore about 0.66 mm. The zero and ninety directions were aligned with the L and LT directions of the aluminium layers. It is to be noted that the unsymmetric lay-up of GLARE3-2/1 causes coupling between membrane and bending characteristics in the laminate.

TEST SPECIMENS AND PROCEDURE

The tensile tests were performed as per the ASTM Standard E8-91 prescribed for metallic materials [4]. The compression properties were determined using the NORTHROP test method [5] commonly employed for laminated composites. The loading was done on a Universal Instron hydraulic testing machine with a capacity of over 85000 N. The loading rate was 2 mm per minute. Wedge action grips with "screen-back" packing were used for holding the tensile specimens. The tension specimens were manufactured in the dog-bone shape prescribed by ASTM E8 with a gauge length of about 64 mm. The compression specimens were 76 mm long and 18 mm wide, with back to back biaxial strain gages. The gauge length for compression specimens was 6.35 mm with clamped end conditions. Load and biaxial strain data were recorded continuously with the Sciometric 200 data acquisition system. At least five specimens were employed in each of the four tests: longitudinal and transverse tension, longitudinal and transverse compression.

TEST RESULTS

ARALL3 TENSION

Typical axial and transverse stress strain curves for ARALL3-3/2 zero and ninety degree specimens are shown in Figures 1 and 2. The average values of the elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio, 0.2% yield stress, ultimate strength and ultimate strain in the L and LT directions are presented in Table 1 along with manufacturer's specifications and previously published data[1]. As expected the ultimate strength and the yield strength of the longitudinally reinforced specimens are much higher than those with transverse reinforcement. The modulus in the ninety degree direction is only about 70% of that in the zero degree direction.

The measured moduli and strength values are in good agreement with the previous test results and manufacturer's data. The most significant discrepancy is between the measured and reported values of ultimate strains for the ninety degree ARALL specimens. This was apparently caused by failure of the strain gauge bonding before ultimate failure of the specimens in the present tests.

The tensile response of the zero degree ARALL specimens is distinctly bilinear as seen in Fig.1. The reduction in stiffness is caused by aluminium yielding, however the fibres continue to carry

the load. The average post yield stiffness of the ARALL3-L specimens was about 23 MPa which is about a third of the initial modulus of 68.9 MPa. In comparison, the yield behaviour of the ninety degree specimens is more gradual being dominated by the properties of the aluminium layers which bear the bulk of the load. The average post yield stiffness of the LT specimens is only about 2.2 MPa, less than 5% of the elastic modulus value of 49.5 MPa. It was also found that the value of the Poisson's ratio of the zero degree specimens increased from 0.33 to 0.36 after yield, while no change was noticeable in the transversely reinforced specimens.

Table 1. Results of Tensile Tests on ARALL and GLARE

Property	Test Dir.	ARALL3			GLARE3		
		NRC Test Data	Manufctr. Data	Published Data[1]	NRC Test Data	Manufctr. Data	Published Data[1]*
Ultim Strength (MPa)	L	737	766	821	646	701	745
	LT	366	365	380	602	715	745
Yield Strength 0.2% (MPa)	L	598	542	607	315	293	303
	LT	323	320	331	282	265	303
Elastic Modulus (GPa)	L	68.9	59.3	66	58.9	57.3	58
	LT	49.5	44.1	49	57.5	53.8	58
Poisson's Ratio (Initial)	L	0.33	**	**	0.27	**	**
	LT	0.26	**	**	0.3	**	**
Ultimate Strain (% strain)	L	1.54	2.37	2.2	**	**	**
	LT	1.64	7.16	8.6	**	**	**

*Note : Data in Ref.1 for GLARE3-3/2

** Not recorded.

GLARE3 TENSION

The results obtained in the tensile tests on the GLARE3-2/1 specimens are also presented in Table 1. The responses of both zero and ninety degree GLARE specimens were noticeably bilinear, similar to the behaviour of zero degree ARALL-3 specimen shown in Fig.1. This is obviously due to the bidirectional fibre reinforcement in GLARE-3. However, the properties in the two directions were not identical (see Table 1).

The modulus and ultimate strength of GLARE3 lie between the corresponding values of ARALL3 in the L and LT directions. However the yield strength of GLARE in both directions are lower than the transverse yield strength of ARALL3 and only about half its value in the fibre direction of ARALL3. This is mainly because the alloy 2024-T3 employed in GLARE-3 has a yield strengths of only 476 MPa whereas the 2024-T3 alloy in ARALL-3 has a yield strength of 545 MPa. After yield the stiffness of GLARE in either direction reduces to about 25% of its original value. No ultimate strain data could be recorded for GLARE as the strain gauges disbonded from the specimens well before their final failure. The ultimate strengths recorded for GLARE are 10 to 15% lower than the manufacturer's data. On the other hand higher values were obtained in the current tests for the yield strengths and the moduli in both directions. The comparison with the previously published values is quite good considering the fact the literature values are for GLARE3-3/2 while laminates tested herein were GLARE3-2/1.

ARALL3 COMPRESSION

The compression test results are presented in Table 2. A typical stress strain response is shown in Fig.3 for a ninety degree specimen. The plot shows that the strains from the front and back sides, which are initially of the same magnitude, begin to diverge dramatically beyond a critical point denoting the onset of buckling in the coupon. Once buckling occurs, bending deformations predominate and there is very little increase in the applied load. Thus the maximum stress was limited by buckling of the coupons and not by material failure. This maximum value is tabulated as the ultimate strength in Table 2.

Before the tests the Euler buckling stress for the specimens was estimated. For a gauge length of 6.35 mm and $E = 49.5$ GPa (the minimum recorded in the tension tests) the buckling stress for simply supported end conditions is obtained as 1830 MPa. For the built-in end conditions employed in the tests, the buckling stress should be four times this value. However the specimens started buckling at significantly lower stress values, around 300 MPa (Fig.3). Assuming that the compressive load is carried solely by the aluminium layers, it is seen that the stress in aluminium reaches its yield value (442 MPa and 469 MPa in L and LT directions respectively for alloy 7475-T76) when the laminate stress is between 300 MPa and 320 MPa. The yielding of the aluminium layers precipitates buckling and hence ultimate failure of the coupons. Thus it is evident that the maximum load carrying capacity of fibre metal laminates in compression is limited by plastic buckling. The fact that the compressive strengths in the fibre direction and perpendicular to it are only marginally different also attests to the minor role played by the prepreg in carrying compressive load.

The present test data is in good agreement with the published data, except that the compressive moduli are 15 to 20% higher. It is to be noted that the compressive strengths reported in Reference 1 were designated as 0.2% proof strengths while the present values are the ultimate (maximum applied) stress values. In general the scatter in the compression test results was much greater than the tension test data. No compression data was provided by the manufacturer.

GLARE3 COMPRESSION

The GLARE 3 compression test results are also listed in Table 2. The stress strain response of GLARE specimens was similar to that of ARALL in compression (Fig.3) except that the divergence between strain data from opposite sides, indicating the bending of the coupons, occurred much earlier. This is due to coupling between axial and bending deformations introduced by the unsymmetry in the zero-ninety lay up of the prepreg in GLARE3-2/1. The applied axial load produces bending right from the start, leading to premature yielding of aluminium and hence failure of the laminate. The compressive strength of unsymmetric laminates is thus much lower than that of symmetric configurations as evidenced by the low values (185 MPa and 173 MPa) for the present specimens in comparison to the 310 MPa reported for GLARE3-3/2 in [1].

Table 2. Results of Tensile Tests on ARALL and GLARE

Property	Test Direction	ARALL3		GLARE3	
		NRC Test Data	Published Data[1]	NRC Test Data	Published Data[1]*
Ultimate Strength (MPa)	L	377	345 (a)	185	310 (a)
	LT	361	366 (a)	173	310 (a)
Elastic Modulus (GPa)	L	78.1	64	65	59
	LT	61.8	50	65.1	59
Poisson's Ratio (Initial)	L	0.32	**	0.28	**
	LT	0.26	**	0.3	**

*Note : Data in Ref.1 for GLARE3-3/2 (a) 0.2% Offset Compressive strength

RULE OF MIXTURES FOR TENSILE BEHAVIOUR

The rule of mixtures formula was used to predict the tensile behaviour of the laminates tested. The average laminate stress σ_{lam} corresponding to an applied strain is computed from the stresses in the aluminium (denoted by subscript al) and the prepreg (subscript pr) as

$$\sigma_{lam} = \frac{\sigma_{al} \cdot t_{al} + \sigma_{pr} \cdot t_{pr}}{t_{al} + t_{pr}}$$

The stresses in the prepreg are obtained from Hooke's law, assuming linear response. The stress σ in aluminium is related to the strain ϵ as per the Ramberg-Osgood formula

$$\epsilon = \frac{\sigma}{E} \left[1 + \frac{3}{7} \left(\sigma / \sigma_{0.7} \right)^{n-1} \right]$$

where E is the Young's modulus. The values of the material parameters 'n' and $\sigma_{0.7}$ for the alloys 7475-T76 and 2024-T3 were obtained from MIL Handbook Vol.5.

EFFECT OF RESIDUAL STRESSES

A quick comparison of the predictions using the rule of mixtures with the ARALL test data showed that while the slopes of the two curves were in good agreement, the theory underestimated the strength of the material, particularly in the zero degree direction. It was therefore felt necessary to take into account the effects of residual stresses in the laminates in the rule of mixtures model. One source of residual stresses is the cooling of the fibre metal laminate after consolidation at a high temperature. The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) in aluminium being higher than that of the prepreg in the fibre direction, this introduces tensile and compressive residual stresses in the aluminium and prepreg layers respectively.

Another source of residual stresses in fibre laminates is the "post-stretching" process which is performed with the deliberate intention of reversing the residual stress state in the laminate. In this process the laminate is mechanically stretched beyond the yield point of aluminium and then released. This introduces residual tensile stresses in the prepreg and compressive stresses in the laminate in the direction of reinforcement. The ARALL3-3/2 employed in the tests had been "post-stretched" in this manner by the manufacturer to a final value of 0.4%. The GLARE laminates supplied were not post-stretched. The rule of mixtures theory was modified to incorporate the residual stresses in the aluminium and prepreg layers of the laminate.

COMPARISON OF THEORY WITH TEST RESULTS

The predictions of the rule of mixtures theory with and without consideration of the residual stresses are presented graphically along with the tensile test data for ARALL-L, ARALL-LT, and GLARE (L) in Figures 4, 5 and 6 respectively. The experimental and theoretical values of the yield strength and the moduli before and after yield are listed in Table 3. The residual stresses affect only the yield points, hence the slopes of the two predicted curves are identical, and in close agreement with the slope of the test curve in each of the four cases.

Table 3. Comparison of Tensile Test Data with Predictions using Rule of Mixtures

		Present Test Results	Rule of Mixtures Predictions	
			without Residual Stresses	with Residual Stresses
ARALL-L	Modulus before yield (GPa)	69	66	66
	Modulus after yield (GPa)	23	22	22
	0.2% Yield Strength (MPa)	598	515	580
ARALL-LT	Modulus before yield (GPa)	49.5	48	48
	Modulus after yield (GPa)	2.2	4.8	4.8
	0.2% Yield Strength (MPa)	323	322	328
GLARE-L	Modulus before yield (GPa)	59	56	56
	Modulus after yield (GPa)	16	13.3	13.3
	0.2% Yield Strength (MPa)	315	314	297
GLARE-LT	Modulus before yield (GPa)	57.5	56	56
	Modulus after yield (GPa)	16	14.5	14.5
	0.2% Yield Strength (MPa)	282	285	268

The predicted value of the 0.2% yield strength rises from 515 MPa to 580 MPa in the case of ARALL-L when the residual stresses due to curing and post-stretch are taken into account (Table 3). The latter value is only 3% lower than the average test value of 598 MPa. However, as seen from the plots in Fig.4, the agreement between theory and test data is even better when the residual stresses due to curing are ignored and only those due to post-stretching is taken into account. In this case the theoretical curve virtually follows the mean of the test data.

In the case of ARALL-LT, GLARE-L and GLARE-LT there is no post-stretching, residual stresses arise only from differential thermal contraction after curing. The influence of these residual stresses is comparatively small (see Figures 5 and 6). However in all three cases the best agreement is obtained when the theory ignores the effect of the residual stresses. Thus all the comparisons unanimously indicated that the rule of mixtures predict the behaviour of fibre metal laminates best when the effects of curing stresses are ignored. However when a laminate is post-stretched the residual stresses due to the post-stretching must be taken into account.

CONCLUSION

The results of tension and compression tests on ARALL3-3/2 and GLARE3-2/1 have been presented. The tension test results are highly consistent and in good agreement with manufacturer's and previously published data. The tensile response along the reinforcement direction is mostly bilinear with a change in stiffness associated with the yielding of the aluminium layers. The compression test results show a greater degree of scatter but are still within 10% of previously reported values for ARALL. The ultimate strength of the unsymmetric laminate GLARE3-2/1 was less than 60% of the values reported for the symmetric GLARE3-3/2.

The compressive strength of fibre metal laminates appears to be limited by the onset of plastic buckling which occurs around the yield point of aluminium in symmetric laminates and earlier in unsymmetric laminates, due to the latter's tendency to bend in the presence of in-plane stresses.

The rule of mixtures accurately predicts the tensile response of fibre metal laminates, particularly when residual stresses due to post-stretching are taken into consideration. Taking into account the thermal residual stresses generated by the curing process appears to reduce the accuracy of the predictions. This phenomenon needs to be further investigated.

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Figure 1. ARALL3-3/2 Zero Degree Tensile Stress Strain Response

Figure 2. ARALL3-3/2 Ninety Degree Tensile Stress Strain Response

Figure 3. ARALL3-3/2 Ninety Degree Compression Stress Strain Response

Figure 4. ARALL3-L Comparison of Test Data with Rule of Mixtures Model

Figure 5. ARALL3-LT Comparison of Test Data with Rule of Mixtures Model

Figure 6. GLARE3-L Comparison of Test Data with Rule of Mixtures Model